

**An Improved PEG-based Molecular Crowding Electrolyte using Zn(TFSI)₂ vs.
Zn(OTf)₂ for Aqueous Zn//V₂O₅ Battery**

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Abstract

Aqueous zinc batteries (AZBs) are promising candidates for scalable and sustainable energy storage applications because of their cost and safety advantages. However, the inevitable parasitic reactions on the Zn anode, mainly attributed to water-induced side reactions, should be solved. Recently, a molecular crowding electrolyte (MCE) strategy has been proposed to mitigate these parasitic reactions, but at a cost of kinetics and thus rate. In this paper, we report an improved Zn//V₂O₅ battery using a newly developed MCE with a crowding agent and 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ as an advanced salt (MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂). Our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ shows enhanced ionic conductivity and ion-transport properties, conferring superior rate capability to Zn//V₂O₅ – releasing 57 vs 0 mAh g⁻¹ at 10C compared to MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, state-of-the-art MCE. Furthermore, due to the decrease in the fraction of ‘free water’ molecules, both MCEs produce an enhanced stability window and an improved reversibility of Zn plating/stripping with superior Coulombic efficiencies compared to the conventional electrolyte (1m Zn(TFSI)₂). Consequently, Zn//V₂O₅ in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ simultaneously delivers superior cycle stability (260 (78%) versus 0 (0%) mAh g⁻¹ (capacity retention)) after 1000 and 350 cycles, respectively, and low self-discharge versus 1m Zn(TFSI)₂. These combined results show that this advanced MCE strategy can be used to design safe, high-reversible, fast, and long-cycled AZBs for practical applications.

Keywords: aqueous Zn-battery; molecular crowding electrolyte; PEG; Zn(TFSI)₂; Zn//V₂O₅

1. Introduction

In the past decades, the utilization and implementation of clean and renewable energy generation (solar, wind, etc.) have experienced a huge and very rapid evolution.[1] However, in order to optimize this sustainable energy production, it must be coupled with a parallel development of energy storage systems, especially due to the intermittent availability of the renewable resources. Therefore, there is a need to develop safe, sustainable, scalable, and stable energy storage systems that can store and manage the power output between peak and off-peak hours. This is only one of the many reasons why the development of aqueous rechargeable battery systems has experienced a significant growth the recent years.[2]

Among them, rechargeable aqueous zinc batteries (AZBs) stand out as candidates for grid-scale energy storage systems because of their safer and low toxic characteristics, simple fabrication process, and moderate energy density. In fact, zinc is an abundant, non-toxic and low-cost (ca USD \$2 kg⁻¹) element, and as a metal anode it possesses some notable advantages such as high theoretical volumetric (5851 mAh cm⁻³) and gravimetric capacities (820 mAh g⁻¹), high redox potential (-0.76 V vs standard hydrogen electrode), simple manufacturing processes and chemical stability in water.[3,4] Despite these merits, the use of Zn metal anode in aqueous electrolyte is still challenging, due to the dendrites formation and complex parasitic reactions such as corrosion, hydrogen evolution, byproducts formation, etc., which lead to low zinc plating/stripping efficiency, and deteriorate performance and battery life, even causing safety issues.[4,5] The main problem is represented by the dendritic growth of the metallic Zn that eventually leads to battery failure.[6] On the other hand, the side-reactions such as Zn anode corrosion and cathodic hydrogen evolution on the metal surface, irreversibly consume electrolyte and generate insoluble byproducts and hydrogen gas. These parasitic reactions not only cause an increase of the electrode polarization of the battery, but the generated gas may elevate internal pressure of the sealed battery and further generate a safety hazard. It is important to note that most of these issues are strongly related to the existence of a large number of “free water” molecules in bulk electrolyte.[7] To address these challenging issues, great efforts have been made

including i) modifications on Zn surface and structure, ii) construction of protective layers onto Zn anodes, and iii) electrolyte engineering using additives and developing more stable Zn salts.[8,9] Among all the cited strategies, electrolyte engineering, which represents a straightforward approach, has become the most promising route to improve the Zn anodic reaction, especially for industrial implementation due to its simplicity.[10]

Although using water-based electrolytes presents important and relevant merits such as non-flammability, low toxicity, and desirable Zn^{2+} storage and transport kinetics, having a large number of free water molecules is detrimental to the battery.[7] The existence of solvated[11,12] and/or free water molecules causes a multitude of parasitic reactions (e.g., water decomposition, Zn corrosion), leading to narrowing of the electrochemical stability window, Zn dendrite formation and deleterious interfacial reactions, as mentioned before.[13] Recently, the “*water-in-salt*” electrolyte (WiSE) strategy has been shown to improve the reversible character of the Zn anode and increase the longevity of AZBs by widening the water stability window, and therefore subsequently curbing the occurrence of water-related side reactions (especially hydrogen evolution reaction; HER).[14,15] However, due to the high cost of the organic metal salts and its high concentration (>20 m LiTFSI) such sophisticated electrolyte can hardly be employed in practical AZBs since it will potentially curtail the economic benefits anticipated for AZBs.[16]

Yet another recent strategy is the use of the concept of “molecular crowding electrolyte” (MCE), which was initially implemented to widen the operation window of aqueous Li based electrolytes.[17] The basic concepts of MCE rely on the use of polyethylene glycol or oxide (simply stated as PEG) as a hydrogen bond donor to effectively decrease the free water molecules in the electrolyte. Contrary to the WiSE concept in which the water molecules are mainly solvated with ions, the water molecules are confined to the crowding agent (PEG) in the MCE.[17] Due to this confinement, the water activity is effectively minimized, thus reducing the water decomposition and further increasing the ESW, but with a much lower cost due to the lower concentration of LiTFSI

(ca., 2 m; m is molality, mol kg⁻¹ versus 21 m for WiSE). Inspired by this strategy, many MCEs have been recently developed, mainly applied in supercapacitors,[18,19] Li-ion[17,20] and rocking chair[21–26] and hybrid Zn-ion batteries.[27]

Although a limited number of rocking chair AZBs using MCEs have appeared in the literature in the last two years, the low ion conductivity, the relatively high viscosity, and the poor electrode wettability of the reported MCEs resulted in moderate cell performance, particularly rate capability, not far from those AZBs that utilize WiSE. Notably, zinc trifluoromethanesulfonate (Zn(OTf)₂) remains the only Zn salt applied in all these examples,[21–26] probably inspired by its high solubility and superior electrochemical and transport properties, attributed to the bulky OTf⁻ (CF₃SO₃⁻) moieties compared to other inorganic Zn salts such as ZnSO₄, ZnCl₂, Zn(ClO₄)₂, etc.[28] In this regard, it is worth highlighting that the choice of Zn salt is a crucial factor, since the Zn plating/stripping efficiency and electrochemical performance of the AZBs are primarily driven by the Zn²⁺ solvation sheath.[29] Therefore, there is still room for further improvement in the performance of AZBs based on MCEs by employing other advanced Zn salts.

Recently, a novel organic salt Zn(TFSI)₂ (TFSI⁻ = [(CF₃SO₂)₂N]⁻; bis trifluoromethanesulfonimide), with more bulky and highly delocalized TFSI anion, has been used for AZBs that also demonstrated a similar improvement to Zn(OTf)₂ in the battery performance.[15,30–32] In these examples, the Zn(TFSI)₂ is used to formulate conventional dilute or concentrated aqueous electrolytes,[30,33] or in most of the cases, applied in combination with additional electrolyte salts to prepare WiSE[15,32,34] or water-in-polymer salt electrolytes.[31]

Here, we investigate the Zn(TFSI)₂ salt in combination with MCE for rocking chair AZBs for the first time – while systematically comparing with the most applied Zn(OTf)₂/MCE combination. With the aim of developing practical AZBs, we utilized commercial V₂O₅ as cathode material to assemble Zn//V₂O₅ aqueous batteries employing the newly developed molecular crowding Zn-based electrolyte. In particular, the effect of the Zn(TFSI)₂ and Zn(OTf)₂ salts in the same molecular

crowding environment (70/30 wt% PEG/H₂O) on battery performance was investigated. We primarily studied the physico-chemical, ion-transport, and structural properties of these electrolytes, supplemented by theoretical calculations. Whenever necessary, we also included a comparison with dilute electrolyte (1m Zn(TFSI)₂) that lacks the PEG crowding agent as the control sample. Then, anode corrosion and Zn plating/stripping behaviour were investigated in detail. Finally, the electrochemical performance of full cells in terms of capacity, rate capability, cycle stability, self-discharge, and float charge characteristics was evaluated, revealing superior performance metrics with the newly developed Zn(TFSI)₂ -based MCE.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Formulation of Molecular Crowding Electrolytes and their Physico-Chemical Characterization

MCEs were formulated by selecting liquid PEG400 (simply stated as PEG) as molecular crowding agent and low salt concentrations (1 or 2 m) of Zn(TFSI)₂ or Zn(OTf)₂ as supporting salts in 70:30 wt% PEG/H₂O solvent (see SI for detailed electrolyte preparation method).

2.1.1. Ion transport properties

We first evaluated the ionic conductivity (σ), the Zn²⁺ transport number ($t_{Zn^{2+}}$) and the electrochemical stability window of the formulated MCEs. The σ of the electrolytes is showed in **Figure 1a** as a function of salt concentration at 25 °C. It is possible to observe that the σ ranges from 1.23 to 0.47 mS cm⁻¹ when Zn(TFSI)₂ is used as salt, while the values are much lower, in the range of 0.83–0.31 mS cm⁻¹ for Zn(OTf)₂. Of note, the value of σ for the conventional electrolyte, 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ is 28.9 mS cm⁻¹, obviously higher than MCEs.

Figure 1. Overall and Zn^{2+} ionic conductivity (a) and Zn^{2+} transport number (b) for 1 or 2m $Zn(OTf)_2$ and $Zn(TFSI)_2$ in 70:30 PEG:H₂O.

The ion transference number is related to the ratio of the charge transported by the Zn^{2+} ionic species to the entire transported charge. Most of the Zn-based electrolytes reported so far show low $t_{Zn^{2+}}$, less than 0.5, mainly due to the simultaneous migration of Zn^{2+} cations and their counter anions, which could increase concentration polarization and minimize cell power density.[8] Figure 1b shows that PEG-based MCEs show higher $t_{Zn^{2+}}$ (0.72–0.86) compared to the literature or with the conventional diluted electrolyte (1m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ with $t_{Zn^{2+}}$ of only 0.1) that was investigated as reference. The $t_{Zn^{2+}}$ increases with the salt concentration, showing a maximum value of 0.86 for the MCE – 2m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ electrolyte. Furthermore, the conductivity of Zn^{2+} cation ($\sigma_{Zn^{2+}}$), i.e., value of σ multiplied with $t_{Zn^{2+}}$, are also reported in Figure 1a. Once again, the conductivity of Zn^{2+} ions in MCE with $Zn(TFSI)_2$ was found to be higher than that with $Zn(OTf)_2$. To correlate these experimental observations, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations (see SI for detailed Computational Methodology) were performed with 1 m aqueous solutions as representative electrolytes, computing the Zn^{2+} diffusion coefficient ($D_{Zn^{2+}}^{electrolyte}$) and $t_{Zn^{2+}}$ the parameters (see Table S2 and Figure S1 in the SI). The $D_{Zn^{2+}}^{electrolyte}$ and $t_{Zn^{2+}}$ for MCE–1m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ were calculated to be nearly 20-fold and 1.4-fold higher, respectively, compared to that in MCE–1m $Zn(OTf)_2$ (0.0784 vs 0.003491 $cm^2\ s^{-1}$ and 0.64 vs 0.47, respectively). In the later section, we will correlate the ion transport properties with the solvation chemistry.

Due to the significant higher ionic conductivity and the competitive Zn^{2+} transference number of MCEs with a salt concentration 1 m, we perform the rest of the experiments only with MEC – 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and MEC – 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$.

3.1.2. Electrochemical stability window

The LSV measurements were performed in three-electrode cells to investigate the electrochemical stability window (ESW) of the formulated electrolytes. As shown in **Figure 2**, the overall stability window of MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ is 0.3 V higher than that of the conventional electrolyte, 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, which is around 2.3 V. When the $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ salt is used in the MCE, the voltage window is approximately 0.4 V higher with respect to the $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, 2.6 vs 2.2 V, respectively. On the anodic side, the onset potential of the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) for the MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ curve shows a positive shift compared to the conventional 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and also compared to MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$. On the cathodic side, the Zn^{2+} deposition process and hydrogen evolution reactions (HER) are taking place inseparably and could occur simultaneously. Therefore, a real onset potential for HER on the cathodic side cannot be accurately estimated, but a negative shift of onset potential for reduction reactions in the case of MCE was evident at sight. The insets of Figure 2 also show that the current density for both the OER (anodic) and the HER (cathodic) processes is lower for the MCE with the $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ salt relative to $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, and both were much lower compared to that in the conventional electrolyte. Specifically, the hydrogen evolution current at 0.05 V was found to be the lowest for MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ compared to other electrolytes tested electrolytes.[27] Furthermore, the Tafel analysis revealed increased overpotential and Tafel slope for MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ compared to the other two electrolytes (Figure S3), suggesting its low catalytic activity and slower kinetics toward parasitic cathodic reactions, respectively. It is worthy to stress that, in these experiments we used platinum disc as the working electrode, which catalyzes the HER reactions. However, in the real battery with Zn metal anode, we anticipate that HER should be lower on account of the higher overpotential of metallic Zn for HER.

Figure 2. Electrochemical stability window, determined by LSV at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} in a three-electrode cell (Pt as working, Zn as counter and reference electrodes).

2.1.3. Raman spectroscopy

To explore how PEG and the different Zn salts influence the ion solvation chemistry in the MCEs, Raman spectra were collected (**Figure 3a** and Figure S4). The most characteristic band is related to the O–H stretching band, located in the region between $3100\text{--}3700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This region can be decomposed into symmetric bands corresponding to water molecules with strong ($\sim 3230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), weak ($\sim 3350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and non H-bonds ($\sim 3560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), respectively.[35] For conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)_2 , a broad band was observed at $3100\text{--}3700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be attributed to various water molecules, with different hydrogen bonds, including a large proportion of “free water” molecules. It is necessary to underline that PEG presents intense bands in the region between 2600 and 3100 cm^{-1} attributed to the symmetric stretching mode of PEG C–H and also two bands in the region of water at 3350 and 3500 cm^{-1} . [35,36] Although this overlapping makes it difficult to quantify water in different H-bond states in the MCEs, a qualitative analysis can still be performed. For example, Figure 3a shows that the presence of PEG in the MCE resulted in the narrowing of the O–H spectral region ($3100\text{--}3700$

cm^{-1}) with the appearance of a new peak at 3547 cm^{-1} , which merges the two other peaks, suggesting that the fraction of “free water” molecules has decreased. Concomitantly, the decrease in the intensity of the peak at 3200 cm^{-1} , related to the strong water-water interactions, confers that the water molecules were trapped by the crowding agent of PEG. Interestingly, the band at $\sim 3560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, related to the non-H-bond, is qualitatively more intense in the MCE containing $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ compared to the $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ counterpart. These results indicate much fewer “free water” molecules in the MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, suggesting that the water activity was reduced more effectively and thus the molecular crowding effect was more impactful in MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$.

Figure 3. Electrolyte structures of CE – 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$. a) Selected Raman spectra between $3050\text{--}3750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, b) a representative MD simulation snapshot for MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, showing water molecules absorbed in the PEG-rich region (c), d–f) typical Zn^{2+} solvation structure and distribution of the water population during the MD simulations (g–i).

2.1.4. Molecular dynamic simulations

We applied MD simulations to examine the microscopic structure of the investigated aqueous electrolytes. Our interest was in the coordination environment of Zn^{2+} cations and the hydrogen-bonding parameters between the water molecules in the bulk of the electrolyte to correlate the estimated percentage of “free water” molecules of MDs with the electrochemistry observed and investigated. Both in conventional electrolyte and in MCE with $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ salt, each Zn^{2+} cation is surrounded by 6 water molecules, while Zn^{2+} is coordinated by 4 OTf^- anions and 2 water molecules in MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ (Figure 3d–f, Figure S2a–c and Table S3). The highly dissociable nature of the $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ salt and the immobilization of TFSI^- are believed to be related to the dominance of the Zn– H_2O coordination.[32,37] While on the contrary, a relatively stronger association of $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ and mobilization of the corresponding OTf^- , leads to the dominance of Zn-anion solvation, which is in good agreement with the previous literature.[21–26] In the recap, these differences in the Zn coordination numbers can explain the changes observed in the calculated diffusion coefficient and transference number of the cations (Table S2). The coordination of zinc with six water molecules in the presence of TFSI^- in solution suggests a higher mobility within the medium and might explain the higher diffusion coefficient ($D_{\text{Zn}^{2+}}$) and $t_{\text{Zn}^{2+}}$ in MCE-1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ than in MCE-1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ that drops to ~2 in the presence of OTf^- .

Further analysis of the hydrogen-bonding patterns revealed that each water molecule forms an average value of 1.80, 1.72 and 1.85 hydrogen bonds with itself in 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, respectively (Table S4). Moreover, the percentage of “free water” molecules can also be calculated by estimating the total number of water molecules that are coordinated to all Zn^{2+} , anion, and PEG species and subtracting it from the total number of water molecules in each system. Figure 3g–i show that, the fraction of “free water” was lower in MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ compared to MCE with 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ and conventional 1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ counterparts (29% vs. 38 and 43%, respectively). This computational analysis is in good agreement with the experimental evidence determined by Raman spectroscopy and can also explain the better electrochemical stability window determined for MCE–1m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$.

2.1.5. Flammability

Although non-flammability is one of the important intrinsic asset of the aqueous electrolytes, the addition of a high content of PEG (70 wt% in our case) could compromise the battery safety advantage.[38] In our preliminary propane-oxygen flame ignition tests, the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ electrolyte infiltrated glass fiber separator was non-flammable, as expected (Video S1). On the contrary, when the glass fiber separator was soaked in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ in PEG electrolyte, it showed a violent burning phenomenon (Video S2). However, under the same conditions, the glass fiber separators infiltrated by MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ (Video S3) and MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (Video S4) exhibited an intermediate burning course that is less violent than in pure PEG and more flammable than in pure water. This can be easily understood: at high temperature flame tests, water will evaporate out quickly and the remaining materials with a high PEG content become flammable.

2.2. Evaluation of MCE towards the Zn anodic reaction

2.2.1. Corrosion of Zn foils

Before testing the electrochemistry of the Zn metal anode in MCEs, we preliminarily investigated on its corrosion behaviour by soaking commercial Zn foil in the three electrolytes. After 14 days of immersion, the surface morphology of Zn was investigated by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). The surface of bare Zn metal is smooth with some grooves that appeared during the scratching process (Figure S5a). In the case of conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, the immersed Zn metal was uneven and covered with large and irregular by-products along with the presence of large corrosion pits, as illustrated in Figure S5b. Figure S5c shows that when Zn(OTf)₂ salt is used in MCE, the pitting corrosion process with randomly distributed by-products was still observed on the Zn metal surface. In contrast, in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, the appearance of by-products was highly minimized and no corrosion pits were observed, which shows that corrosion was severely suppressed in this MCE (Figure S5d). These observations were confirmed with X-ray diffraction (XRD) that evidenced the formation of various zincate by-products, in agreement with previous studies,[39] for

the Zn foil immersed in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ electrolytes (Figure S6). Differently, in the case of MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, such by-products were absent and its XRD spectrum was almost similar to that of the bare Zn.

2.2.2. Assessment of Zn plating/stripping reactions

The reversibility of the Zn plating/stripping was first investigated using cyclic voltammetry (CV) as shown in **Figure 4a**. All electrolytes reveal a reversible electrochemical stripping/plating process of Zn with an improved coulombic efficiency of 91% for MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ and 96% for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to a lower 77% for the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ electrolyte. Moreover, while comparing the area under CV curves for MCEs, an improved Zn yield is observed for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ over MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ due to higher ionic conductivity in the former electrolyte (Figure 1a).[40]

Figure 4. Preliminary Zn plating assessment. a) Cyclic voltammograms of Zn nucleation on the Pt electrode. The current intensity for 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ was divided by 150-factors for better visualization. In the inset, a zoom-in for the nucleation potential region is illustrated. b) Nucleation and growth of plated Zn, monitored by GCD in Zn//Cu asymmetrical cells at 0.1 mA cm⁻². c) Chronoamperograms of the Zn anode at a -0.1 V overpotential.

Furthermore, the crossover characteristics of CV profiles were used to determine the overpotential of nucleation (NOP) that serves as a reference to understand the mechanism of Zn²⁺ electrodeposition at the nucleation stage. When comparing the NOPs of the electrolytes, we can observe that the NOP for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, is higher by approximately 59 and 30 mV compared to MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ and 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, respectively (Figure S7 and the associated note). Also, Zn//Cu cells were used to obtain additional information on Zn²⁺ ion deposition, nucleation, and growth processes. As shown in Figure 4b at 0.1 mA cm⁻², the NOP for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ is higher

than in the other electrolytes, and at higher currents of 0.25 and 0.5 mA cm⁻², again at least higher than in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (Figure S8 and the associated note). Since a higher overpotential corresponds to the formation of finer crystal nuclei, uniform deposition is probably easier to achieve in our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂.^[41] Despite this favourable higher NOP for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, the growth potential is also lower compared to that in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ (Figure 4b and S8), which would be beneficial for lowering the voltage polarization of the battery.

Finally, chronoamperometry measurements were carried out on Zn//Zn cells at – 0.1, – 0.15, – 0.2, and – 0.25 V to study the Zn²⁺ ion diffusion behavior at the surface of the Zn electrode (Figure 4c and S9). In general, for the symmetric cells in MCEs, the currents were significantly lower and gradually stabilized through the three-dimensional (3D) diffusion process after a short two-dimensional (2D) diffusion time, suggesting their effectiveness in stabilizing the Zn anode. On the other hand, the current of Zn//Zn cells in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ rapidly increases at the beginning of Zn deposition, followed by a transient stabilization period, and then continuously increase. Such current-time profiles are a typical of the prolonged and rampant 2D diffusion procedure of Zn²⁺ ions nucleation active sites, corresponding to uneven deposition and dendritic growth.^[42] All these preliminary studies reveal the efficacy of MCEs, particularly our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, to achieve smoother Zn²⁺ electrodeposition compared to the conventional electrolyte that lacks the crowding agent.

Figure 5. Comparative Zn anode performance. Coulombic efficiencies of Zn//Cu asymmetric cells at different areal capacities and at a fixed areal current of 0.250 mA cm^{-2} (a), and at different areal currents and at a fixed areal capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} (b). c) Zn plating/stripping in Zn//Zn symmetric cell at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} and 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} .

In order to fully assess the rechargeability of the Zn anode, we assembled Zn//Cu asymmetric cells to quantify the reversibility of Zn plating/stripping by looking at the coulombic efficiency parameter. First, we tested asymmetric cells at variable areal capacities in the range of $0.05\text{--}2.5 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2}$ at a fixed 0.25 mA cm^{-2} current density (Figure 5a and Figure S7). The coulombic efficiencies for MCE-1m Zn(TFSI)₂ were stable in the range of 95–99% throughout the range of capacities, while lower values (below 95%) were obtained below 1 mAh cm^{-2} for MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂. On the contrary, the coulombic efficiencies of the conventional electrolyte, 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, did not exceed 95%, even during the less severe test conditions (below 1 mAh cm^{-2}), further dropping off to much lower values under practical, higher capacities. This suggests that severe parasitic reactions that occurred simultaneously during Zn deposition/removal are minimized in our MCE electrolyte - 1m Zn (TFSI)₂, particularly while compared to the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂.

Then, to evaluate the kinetics of the Zn plating/stripping reactions, we fixed the areal capacity to 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} and tested asymmetrical cells at variable current densities (Figure 5b and Figure S8). Our MCE-1m Zn(TFSI)₂ rendered stable operation with superior coulombic efficiencies simultaneously in both low ($0.05\text{--}0.25 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) and high ($0.5\text{--}2 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) current regimes, particularly compared to conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ in the low- and MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂ in high-current conditions, respectively. Furthermore, when the cells subjected to a higher current of 3.5 mA

cm^{-2} , Zn//Cu was still operational in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ while it did not work in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ at such high currents. Furthermore, voltage polarization (Figure S8d), augmented monotonically with increasing current for both MCEs, but more drastically in the case of Zn(OTf)₂, suggesting a superior rate capability for the Zn(TFSI)₂ based MCE, in accordance with their better transport properties.

The surface morphology of Zn and copper substrates was investigated by FE-SEM after 15 cycles at 1 mA cm^{-2} with a discharge/charge capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} in a Zn//Cu cell, followed by the final Zn²⁺ deposition cycle. Interestingly, the stripped Zn surface presented a more uniform stripping without discernible corrosion pits in the MCEs whereas nonuniformities of stripping with variable corrosion pits can be easily seen in the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, as illustrated in Figure S12. The XRD patterns of the Zn anode further substantiated fewer by-products in the MCEs, while in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, new peaks corresponding to by-products are once again apparent (Figure S13).

Moreover, the uneven distribution of different-shaped Zn deposits on the copper substrate can be appreciated with mossy structure, larger by-products and protrusions in the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, (Figure S14). However, more uniform deposition of zinc with a smooth flat copper electrode can be observed when MCEs are used. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (Figure S15–17) confirms that the solid deposits were made of Zn, C, O, F, and S elements with a relatively higher proportion of Zn (compared to Cu) and a smaller proportion of O and C (compared to Zn) in MCEs. This confirms the better uniformity of the plated Zn and fewer zincates, respectively, compared to that in conventional electrolyte.

Finally, the behaviour of these electrolytes towards Zn semi-reaction was investigated in Zn//Zn symmetric cells that were galvanostatically cycled at 0.5 mA cm^{-2} and 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} (Figure 5c). Due to the higher viscosity and lower ionic conductivity of the MCEs, the average voltage polarization was approximately 141 and 163 mV in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, respectively, while it was only 30 mV in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂. However, in the latter electrolyte, apparent voltage fluctuation and subsequent premature cell failure were observed after

cycling only for 270 hours, while cells with the MCEs sustained up to 700 hours with an at least 2.5-fold enhanced cumulative capacity of 175 mAh cm^{-2} (versus 68 mAh cm^{-2} for conventional 1 m Zn(TFSI)_2). A similar cycling behaviour can also be observed when Zn//Zn cells were cycled at a higher capacity of 1 mAh cm^{-2} at the same 0.5 mA cm^{-2} current density (Figure S18).

From all this electrochemical investigation of Zn anode, we can reasonably conclude that the addition of PEG into the aqueous electrolyte significantly inhibits the side reactions (water splitting, corrosion, etc.) and enables less dendritic Zn plating/stripping that would otherwise be detrimental for practical application of ZMBs.

2.3. Zn/ V_2O_5 Full Cell Tests

2.3.1. Rate performance

Figure 6. Comparative Zn/ V_2O_5 full cell rate performance from 0.5 to 10C in different electrolytes. a-c) Charge/discharge voltage profiles, and the corresponding specific discharge capacity versus cycle number at different C-rates (d).

With the aim of investigating the feasibility of MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ to construct an improved battery over the other electrolytes, we assembled and tested Zn//V₂O₅ full cells. The rate performance of Zn//V₂O₅ in all these electrolytes was evaluated (**Figure 6**), in which we can see how after an activation period of 30 cycles, MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ delivered excellent rate capabilities with reversible capacities of 257, 236, 208, 162, 133, 94 and 33 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10C, respectively. In the case of MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, the capacity values were lower (179, 165, 154, 114, 94 and 57 at 0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 3 and 5C), and the battery was unable to operate at 10C, indicating a better rate performance in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂. Additionally, coulombic efficiencies were also higher and more stable in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (Figure S19a). Furthermore, when the C rate was brought back to 0.5C, near quantitative capacity recovery was observed to their pre-conditioning value was observed for the full cells in both MCEs. However, a significant loss of capacity during the cycling period and poor capacity recovery was observed for the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂. In Figure 6a–c two distinct sloping charge/discharge profiles, which are associated with the well-known two reaction processes of the Zn²⁺/H⁺ intercalation/deintercalation in the V₂O₅ cathode, were observed in all cases.[5,43] Furthermore, the average discharge voltage (0.74 versus 0.70 V; Figure S19b,c) was calculated to be slightly higher by 40 mV in the MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to that in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂. Due to this voltage gain and the attainability of higher capacity synergy in our MCE–1m Zn (TFSI)₂, Zn//V₂O₅ could reach high specific energy of 189.7 Wh kg_{cathode}⁻¹, which is a promising number for aqueous batteries.

The comparative kinetic aspects of electro-ionic reactions within the V₂O₅ cathode between the MCEs were investigated by combined electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and CV studies. The reduced charge transfer resistance of the V₂O₅ cathode in TFSI-based MCE can be reflected in Nyquist plots (**Figure 7a**). The results of the EIS fitting calculation reveal that the equivalent series resistance (R_s), the charger transfer resistance at electrode/electrolyte (R_{ct}) and the Warburg diffusion impedance (σ_w) of V₂O₅ in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ are 37 Ω , 370 Ω and 16 Ω s^{-1/2}, respectively, which are lower than those of

MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂ (47 Ω, 822 Ω and 28 Ω s^{-1/2}, respectively). As σ_w is inversely proportional to the ion diffusivity, a higher ionic conductivity is thus expected in TFSI-based MCE over OTf. Subsequently, the diffusivity of Zn²⁺ in the V₂O₅ electrode ($D_{\text{Zn}^{2+}}^{\text{electrode}}$) was determined by GITT measurement (Figure 7b). In general, $D_{\text{Zn}^{2+}}^{\text{electrode}}$ diffusivity at each state-of-charge and depth-of-discharge was higher in TFSI-based MCE, with an average value of 6.8 vs 1.7 x 10⁻⁹ and 11.3 vs 2.2 x 10⁻⁹ cm² s⁻¹ (MCE-1m Zn(TFSI)₂ vs MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂) for charging and discharging cycles, respectively, thus corroborated the EIS results. CV profiles (Figure 7c, d) clearly show the two peaks associated to with the two well-known reaction processes of the Zn²⁺/H⁺ intercalation/deintercalation in the V₂O₅ cathode, also evidenced in charge-discharge experiments (Figure 6a-c). Analysis of CVs at various scan rates was performed to determine kinetic parameters such as the heterogeneous reaction rate constant (k^0), from the ν -dependence of the peak potentials using the Laviron method. The k^0 for V₂O₅ was calculated to be about 1.7-fold higher in MCE-1m Zn(TFSI)₂ than in MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂ (0.5 vs 0.3 ms⁻¹; Figure 7e). Considering the physical significance of k^0 , the redox system with the highest k^0 reaches reaction equilibrium faster and thus exhibiting facilitated redox kinetics. The CV analysis was further extended to obtain the b -values from the power-law analysis. The b -value close to 0.5 suggests that the electrochemical process is principally controlled by the diffusion process, while the b -value close to 1.0 indicates the dominant role of the capacitive process. A relatively high b -value of 0.71/0.76 in MCE-1m Zn(TFSI)₂ versus 0.59/0.57 in MCE-1m Zn(OTf)₂ for the oxidation (O2)/reduction (R2) peaks (Figure 7f), suggests that the overall redox response tends to be more diffusion-limited in the OTf-based MCE.[44]

Figure 7. Comparative electrochemical kinetic evaluation of Zn/V₂O₅ in MCEs. a) Nyquist plots, along with an equivalent circuit model used to fit the EIS data. b) $D_{Zn^{2+}}$ diffusivity as a function of SOC/DOD (bottom range) calculated from GITT measurement (top range). c, d) CVs at different scan rates in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (c) and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ (d). e) Laviron plots: indicating the variation of anodic and cathodic peak positions (E_p) as a function of the scan rate (on a logarithmic scale). f) Peak current vs scan rate on the logarithmic scale to obtain b-values according to $i_p = av^b$.

In summary, the less diffusion-limited current response due to faster redox reactions (higher k^0), the facile charge-transfer process (lower R_{ct}) and facilitated ion mobility (higher $D_{Zn^{2+}}^{electrode}$) should impart a superior dynamic behavior to V₂O₅ cathode in TFSI-based MCE. In addition, optimistically, the kinetics of Zn stripping/plating was also faster in the TFSI-MCE compared to those of OTf. Therefore, benefiting collectively from the superior rate performance at the anode and the cathode ends, Zn/V₂O₅ complete cells exhibited improved rate capability in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂.

2.3.2. Cycle stability

After the rate capability experiments, the same cells were subjected to long cycling at 2C (Figure S20). After 1000 cycles, Zn/V₂O₅ sustained high capacities of 137 and 101 mAh g⁻¹ in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, which corresponds to an excellent capacity retention of 85 and

80%, respectively. Moreover, the cycling test of the same cell in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ is not meaningful, since it already has lost most of its capacity during the rate capability experiment, and delivered insignificant capacities while cycling at 2C.

Figure 8. Comparative Zn//V₂O₅ full cell cycle stability performance in different electrolytes. (a, b) Specific discharge capacity versus cycle number at 0.5C at a negative-to-positive (N/P) capacity ratio of 40/1 and electrolyte-to-capacity (E/C) ratio of 110 µl mAh⁻¹ (a), and N/P = 40/1 and E/C = 20 µl mAh⁻¹ (b).

To fairly compare the cycle stability of the full cells in all of these electrolytes, fresh cells were assembled and tested at a low C-rate of 0.5 C (**Figure 8a**). Akin to the cycling tests results at 2C, once again Zn//V₂O₅ in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ delivered a high initial capacity of 330 mAh g⁻¹ (versus 200 mAh g⁻¹ for MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂), and sustained up to 260 mAh g⁻¹ (versus 158 mAh g⁻¹) for 1000 cycles while operational for 108 days (versus 940 cycles and 84 days) with an impressive similar capacity retention of 78% (versus 79%). Considering the longevity of the cycling experiments with remarkable capacity retention, the capacity decay rates were calculated to be 0.022% per cycle and 0.20% per day in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ versus 0.022% per cycle and 0.25% per day in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂. On the contrary, despite its initial high capacity, Zn//V₂O₅ in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ electrolyte exhibited a continuous capacity fade that eventually drastically drops after 365 cycles (45 days of operation). Evidently, the capacity decay rates of 0.27% per cycle and 2.2% per day for the conventional electrolyte were much higher compared to the MCEs.

In previous Zn//V₂O₅ cycling experiments, we used a high electrolyte-to-capacity (E/C) ratio of 110 $\mu\text{l mAh}^{-1}$ and a negative-to-positive (N/P) capacity ratio of 40/1, which is not encouraging from the point of view of practicability. To make Zn//V₂O₅ as practical as possible, first, we reduced E/C ratio to 20 $\mu\text{l mAh}^{-1}$, while keeping the same N/P ratio, i.e., 40/1. Before discussing the results, we would like to clarify a couple of aspects here. While compared to Li-ion and Li-S batteries, lean electrolyte conditions are not well established for Zn batteries, hence we used 20 $\mu\text{l mAh}^{-1}$ as our convenient lean electrolyte formulation. Then, to work with such lean electrolyte condition, we switched from using a glass fiber (Whatman GF/D) (which was used in all the previously experiments) to thin cellulose filter paper. Therefore, the cycling experiments under these two conditions with different separators are not directly comparable. The Zn//V₂O₅ full cell in our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ under this lean electrolyte condition, not only delivered a higher initial capacity, but also maintained a superior capacity retention of 99% than those in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ (92%) and 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (35%) after 125 cycles at 0.5C (Figure 8b). Finally, in this lean electrolyte condition, we decreased the N/P ratio to 4/1 and carried out cycling tests at 0.5C (Figure S21). Once again, Zn//V₂O₅ in our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, attained a higher capacity and retained 82% (versus 40%) of its initial capacity over 125 cycles compared to MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, probably because of better wettability and improved ion transport properties in the TFSI-based MCE over OTf. However, as expected, the cycling performance of Zn//V₂O₅ in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, was the worst that cycled for only 50 cycles before losing all its capacity. These results highlight the advantage of our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ over conventional and most applied OTF-based molecular crowding electrolytes under practically relevant conditions.

The coulombic efficiencies of the Zn//V₂O₅ full cells in both MCEs were stable and maintained around 99.9% during cycling under all conditions tested (Figure S20b, S22), while certain fluctuations with lower values (97–98.5%) were observed in the conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂. Moreover, the initial coulombic efficiencies (in 10 cycles) were also quantitative in both MCEs, particularly in our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, while lower values (85–95%) were attained in 1m

Zn(TFSI)₂. From these results, and also supported by previous study in this context,[45] we can hypothesize that the parasitic reactions, including HER are greatly suppressed in both the MCEs compared to the conventional electrolyte that lacks the crowding agent. Moreover, from the shape charge/discharge curves (Figure S23–26) we can confirm the superior stability and higher reversibility of the battery in the MCEs over conventional electrolyte that feature relatively lower IR-drop and voltage polarization that seemed to less augment upon cycling, particularly in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂.

In order to understand the superior cyclability of Zn//V₂O₅ in MCEs over conventional dilute electrolyte, post-mortem analysis of both the Zn anode and V₂O₅ cathode from the cycled cells was carried out. The post-cycled Zn anode in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ showed apparent corrosion pits, cracks, and many aggregated schistose by-products, along with dendrites (Figure S27a–c and S28). On the other hand, the Zn anodes were almost free of these aforementioned detrimental features, still exhibiting relatively smooth, almost dendrite-free, and uniform surface morphologies in both MCEs (Figure S27d–i). Additionally, many black pits on the separator surface of the anode side suggest severe dendritic Zn and loosely connected dead Zn in 1m Zn (TFSI)₂, while the separators in both the MCEs presented usual texture free from black pits (Figure S29). Furthermore, EDS mapping revealed a relatively lower proportion of O (compared to Zn) in both MCEs, indicating a smaller population of zincates compared to that in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ (Figure S30–32). Finally, the XRD patterns of the post-cycled Zn anodes were almost similar to the pristine Zn in both MCEs, while that of Zn in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ was dominated by diffraction peaks of ZnO or zincate species, which corroborated the EDS results (Figure S33).

On the cathode side, the phase transformation and ubiquitous dissolution mechanisms of α -V₂O₅ in aqueous Zn electrolytes are proposed as the most common reasons, leading to structural degradation and subsequent attenuated stability.[46,47] Firstly, the higher dissolution of V₂O₅ in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ is very apparent from the coloration on the separator surface of both the anode and the

cathode sides (Figure S29). The dissolved vanadium species passed through the separator and was deposited on the Zn anode, as revealed by the presence of a significant fraction of V (8% compared to Zn) (Figure S30). Whereas, the separators in both the MCEs were almost colorless (Figure S29), and an insignificant amount of V was detected on the Zn anodes of the post-cycled Zn//V₂O₅ cells in MCEs (Figure S31, S32).

Second, we analyzed the surface morphology of the post-cycled V₂O₅ cathode by FE-SEM, revealing that the morphology in the MCEs was almost similar to that of pristine, retaining its intrinsic well inter-connected particle network characteristics (Figure S34e–p). However, in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, formation of cracks, indicating the structural collapse, and mossy and porous passivation layer, probably because of by-products deposition was observed (Figure S34a–d).

Finally, XRD was employed to study the extent of by-products formation on the cathode upon cycling in all of these electrolytes. The intensity of typical diffraction peaks of V₂O₅ were greatly decreased for the post-cycled V₂O₅ cathode in 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, along with the appearance of prominent new diffraction peaks at 12.5° and 30.1° (Figure S38). However, optimistically, the intensity of these diffraction peaks was substantially lower in both MCEs. The appearance of these impurity peaks in the post-cycled V₂O₅ cathode XRD pattern can be reasonably assigned to a well-established alkali-type by-product formation process (*vide supra*). In conventional electrolyte, due to the high fraction of active water in contact with V₂O₅, the co-intercalation of H⁺ with Zn²⁺ is most likely to occur, thus resulting in a dramatic increase in the concentration of OH⁻ near the cathode-electrolyte interface, causing the formation of zincate and ZnO by-products. Due to the PEG-mediated water crowding that effectively minimized water activity, the extent of by-product formation was greatly diminished in the case of post-cycled V₂O₅ cathode in both MCEs, as evidenced by the lower intensity of such impurity peaks.

Therefore, based on post-mortem analysis, the enhanced cycle stability of Zn//V₂O₅ in MCEs over conventional electrolyte can be attributed to the buffering of “water activity” of MCEs. This was

collectively reflected both anode side and cathode side, preventing the occurrence of detrimental parasitic reactions and the growth of dendrites for the Zn anode and dissolution of the V_2O_5 cathode and by-products formation on its surface. However, we emphasize that since $Zn(TFSI)_2$ is relatively a new salt for Zn batteries, the exact composition of by-products is still unknown. We agree that more detailed studies are needed to fully characterize the by-products, reveal their formation mechanism and uncover their influence on underlying charge storage mechanism of V_2O_5 cathode.

3.3.3. Self-Discharge and Float Charge Experiments

The self-discharge characteristic of $Zn//V_2O_5$ was evaluated by monitoring the change of open-circuit voltage (OCV) for a fully charged battery during 24 h of rest period and then discharged to 0.1 V (**Figure 9a**). Interestingly, the cells in both MCEs exhibited low self-discharge of 2 and 7% in MCEs based on TFSI and OTf, respectively, whereas, a severe self-discharge (approx. 32%) was observed in the conventional 1m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ (Figure 9b). Furthermore, extending the resting period to 384 h did not drastically affect self-discharge, with only a slight increase to 11 and 14% in TFSI and OTf-based MCEs, respectively (Figure S39). On the contrary, cell in CE – 1m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ lost 94% of its initial capacity during the same period of resting. This impressive anti-self-discharge behavior of $Zn//V_2O_5$, particularly in MCE–1m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ was compared with state-of-the-art Zn-V aqueous batteries (Table S6). A low self-discharge rate of 0.029% per hour is much lower than the reported Zn-V batteries (Figure 9c).

Figure 9. Comparative self-discharge characteristics of Zn//V₂O₅ evaluated by charging the cell to 100% SOC at 0.5 C, resting for 24 h, followed by discharging at 0.5C. a) OCV monitoring during resting time. b) The corresponding voltage-normalized capacity profiles. c) Comparison in terms of self-discharge rate with the state-of-the-art Zn-V aqueous batteries. The references (numbers) in the figure correspond to the entries in Table S6. The 8 entry corresponds to the MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ reported here.

Furthermore, a floating charge current test was carried out after galvanostatically charged at 0.5C to 1.7 V, followed by constant voltage charging of 1.7 V for 24 h (Figure S40a). The potentiostatic floating charge currents of Zn//V₂O₅ in the MCEs dropped to less than 1 mA g⁻¹ in 3 h and became stable, reaching 0.77 and 0.81 mA g⁻¹ after 24 h for MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, respectively (Figure S40b). However, a two-fold excess float charge current of 1.6 mA g⁻¹ was observed for Zn//V₂O₅ in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂, indicating the superior anti-self-discharge characteristic of MCEs over the conventional electrolyte. Furthermore, a substantial discharge capacity loss of 56% (compared to charge capacity) was observed for Zn//V₂O₅ in conventional 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ after float charge (Figure S40c). In contrast, cells in MCEs showed small

loss of discharge capacities of approximately 12%, once again suggesting superior immunity towards the self-discharge.[48]

This low self-discharge rate and superior float charge performance confer the parasitic reactions (e.g., water electrolysis, corrosion of Zn) and dissolution of the active cathode active-material are potentially suppressed with the MCEs.[48,49] These advantages definitely bring the possibility of exploiting our advanced MCEs in practical batteries for large-scale applications.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we demonstrated the efficacious combination of the Zn(TFSI)₂ salt and the PEG-based molecular crowding agent to formulate advanced electrolytes for the development of an improved Zn//V₂O₅ aqueous battery. Various physico-chemical and electrochemical properties of this electrolyte (MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂) are compared with conventional diluted electrolyte (1m Zn(TFSI)₂) – that lacks the crowding agent and another molecular crowding electrolyte (MCE) with Zn(OTf)₂ salt – that widely investigated in the literature (MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂) as control samples. Our MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, (i) exhibited enhanced ionic conductivity and ion-transport properties compared to MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ and (ii) was able to minimize the detrimental side reactions such as HER, metal corrosion, by-products, and dendrite formation compared to CE – 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂. The former and latter improvements were reflected in the kinetics (rate) and overall performance (cycle, self-discharge, etc.) of the battery, respectively. In general, the fraction of “free water” molecules in the electrolyte was reduced as confirmed by combined Raman and Molecular Dynamics simulation in both MCEs compared to the conventional electrolyte. This beneficial effect eventually led to the enhanced electrochemical stability window, improved reversibility, and stability for the Zn plating/stripping process with superior coulombic efficiencies.

The assembled Zn//V₂O₅ full batteries with the MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂, not only delivered an initial high specific capacity of 257 mAh g⁻¹ (vs 179 mAh g⁻¹) at 0.5C, but also attained 57 mAh g⁻¹

at 10C, whereas the battery in MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂ was not able to operate at this C-rate, indicating better rate performance in our electrolyte owing to the faster redox kinetics, facile charge-transfer process and facilitated Zn-ion mobility. Furthermore, full cells in MCEs demonstrated much superior cycle stability at 0.5C – retaining 78 and 79% of their initial capacity, but delivering 260 and 158 mAh g⁻¹ after 1000 and 940 cycles in MCE–1m Zn(TFSI)₂ and MCE–1m Zn(OTf)₂, respectively. However, the battery in CE – 1m Zn(TFSI)₂ exhibited continuous capacity fading and eventually lost all of its capacity after 365 cycles. Finally, the low self-discharge rate and superior float charge behavior suggested that the detrimental parasitic reactions are suppressed in our battery with MCEs compared to the conventional electrolyte. We believe that the results presented here will provide an upgraded route toward the formulation of advanced aqueous electrolytes for the development of improved Zn metal batteries and put forward the emerging field of MCEs.

Appendix A. Supplementary Data

Supporting table, Experimental Section and Figs are in Supporting Information.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

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